

Action of Sodium, Potassium, and Ammonium Hydroxide Solutions on Etheral Blue Peroxychromic Acid and its Pyridine Complex

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From the decomposition of the etheral blue peroxychromate in water and in NaOH, KOH, and NH₄OH solutions, it has been concluded that the blue perchromate contains hexavalent as well as trivalent chromium. A similar study of its pyridine complex has also been made with the same result.

Barreswil¹ observed that the blue compound, obtained by adding H₂O₂ to chromic acid or acidified K₂Cr₂O₇, afforded alkali chromates when its etheral solution was treated with alkali solutions. According to Aschoff², addition of KOH to the etheral blue compound led to the evolution of oxygen with the formation of yellow potassium chromate. Similarly with lead oxide, lead chromate was formed. Schonbein³ and Martinon⁴, as well as O' Wiede⁵, also arrived at the conclusion that etheral blue perchromate, on being treated with alkali hydroxides, formed corresponding chromates.

None of the above workers tried to correlate the reaction between the etheral blue perchromate and alkali hydroxides with its constitution. An attempt has been made in the present communication to arrive at a definite conclusion regarding the constitution of the blue perchromate on the basis of the above reactions. A similar reaction of alkalis has also been observed with the pyridine complex of the blue perchromate.

EXPERIMENTAL

The reagents employed were all of A.R. quality. Blue perchromate was prepared by adding H₂O₂ (varying quantities) to 5% acidified dichromate (75 ml) and extracted with ether (150 ml). After washing with ice-cold water, water was frozen by keeping the etheral extract in a refrigerator and then transferred to a dry and cold flask, kept in ice. The following studies were made.

Each of the blue compound (5 ml) was allowed to decompose (i) in water (20 ml) in two Erlenmeyer flasks, (ii) in water in two closed flasks, (iii) in 1*N*-NaOH, KOH, and NH₄OH respectively. (iv) Definite weights of the pyridine complex prepared with 50 ml of the above blue compound by O' Wiede's method⁵ were allowed to decompose similarly in

1. *Ann. chim. phys.*, 1848, 29, 364; *Compt. rend.*, 1849, 18, 1065.
2. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1860, i, 81, 402; *Chem. News*, 1861, 5, 129.
3. *J. prakt. Chem.*, 1860, i, 80, 257.
4. *Bull. soc. chim.*, 1886, 45, 862.
5. *Ber.*, 1897, 30, 2178.

water, NaOH, KOH, and NH_4OH solutions, respectively. The blue compound (5 ml) was titrated against a standard ($N/20$) thiosulphate solution in two stages in the following manner: (a) after treatment with KI to a pale yellow end point with starch, (b) followed by titration with addition of fresh dilute H_2SO_4 to a green end point with starch.

After about 4 hr. the blue compound and its complex were found to have decomposed in each case and the products so obtained were then treated as follows: (1) Contents of one of the flasks were titrated iodometrically after adding KI and H_2SO_4 . (2) Contents of the other flasks were oxidised by 100 vol. H_2O_2 in NaOH and then titrated iodometrically.

Similarly titrations were carried out with the decomposition product of the pyridine complex in water and alkali hydroxide solutions.

TABLE I

$5\% \text{K}_2\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7 = 75 \text{ ml. } 2N\text{-H}_2\text{SO}_4 = 10 \text{ ml. Ether} = 150 \text{ ml.}$
Varying quantities of 20 vol. H_2O_2 and $N/20\text{-Na}_2\text{S}_2\text{O}_3$ were used.

Vol. of H_2O_2 used.	Thiosulphate (ml) used in Blue compound.		used in W.D.P.	titrating W.D.P. oxidised.	$\frac{b+c}{d}$.	$\frac{a}{d}$ or $\frac{e}{d}$.	$\frac{e}{e}$.	$\frac{b+c}{e}$.
a	b	c	d	e	f	g	h	i
10	2.05	2.90	2.40	2.90	2.06	1.21	1.00	1.70
25	6.10	6.60	7.70	9.60	2.16	1.25	1.00	1.63
25	5.75	9.15	7.45	9.10	2.00	1.23	1.00	1.63
			C.B.D.P.	C.B.D.P. oxidised.				
10	2.05	2.90	1.45	2.90	3.41	2.00	1.00	1.79
25	6.10	9.60	4.60	9.60	3.28	2.00	1.00	1.63
25	5.75	9.15	4.55	9.10	3.25	2.00	1.00	1.63
			NaOH-D.P.	NaOH-D.P. oxidised.				
10	2.05	2.90	2.90	2.90	1.70	1.00	1.00	1.71
25	6.10	9.60	9.20	9.60	1.70	1.04	1.00	1.63
25	5.75	9.15	8.75	9.10	1.72	1.04	1.00	1.63
			KOH-D.P.	KOH-D.P. oxidised.				
10	2.05	2.90	2.90	2.90	1.74	1.00	1.00	1.70
25	6.10	9.60	9.60	9.60	1.63	1.00	1.00	1.63
25	6.75	9.15	8.65	9.15	1.72	1.00	1.00	1.63
			NH_4OH -D.P.	NH_4OH -D.P. oxidised.				
10	2.05	2.90	2.40	8.20	2.00	1.20	0.25	3.40
25	6.10	9.60	8.60	14.70	1.70	0.99	0.65	1.70
25	5.75	9.15	8.00	20.00	1.86	0.87	0.90	3.75

N.B. W. D. P. = water-decomposition product.
C.B.D.P. = closed bottle decomposition product.
D. P. = decomposition product.

TABLE II

Pyridine complex.

Py complex	This used for Py complex & H ₂ SO ₄ (dil.)	This calc. for 1 g. of Py complex.
a	b	c
0.0094 g.	5.05 ml	587.60 ml
0.0100	5.37	585.00
0.0112	6.50	582.00
		Mean 584.00

Py complex decom. in water.	This for 10 ml of made up soln.	This for 1g. of Py complex.	This for 10 ml. of made up soln. oxidised.	This for 1g. of Py complex.
d	e	f	g	h
0.2108 g.	1.90	225.0ml	2.60	308.00
0.2112	1.95	230.8	2.70	318.60,
0.2220	2.05	230.7	2.75	309.00
		Mean 228.6		Mean 312.20

Decomposition product of Py complex in NaOH/KOH.

l	j	k	l	m
0.2003 g.	2.55 ml	318.00 ml	2.55	318.00 ml
0.2102	2.70	320.00	2.70	320.00
0.2244	2.85	318.50	2.85	318.00
		Mean 318.50		Mean 318.60

Decomposition product of Py complex in NH₄OH.

n	o	p	q	r
0.2004	2.50	311.80	Unlimited	Unlimited
0.2106	2.80	318.10	"	"
0.2402	3.00	312.20	"	"

TABLE III

Summary of Table II.

$\frac{a}{f}$	$\frac{a}{b}$	$\frac{h}{f}$	$\frac{h}{k}$ or $\frac{h}{m}$
A	B	C	D
2.24	1.71	1.36	1.000

DISCUSSION

The observations recorded in the above tables show that (i) there is an increase in the titration value on oxidation by H₂O₂ in NaOH over that when the substance or its pyridine complex is decomposed in NaOH or KOH; (ii) there is a large increase in the titration value if the blue compound is decomposed in NH₄OH on oxidation with 100 vol. H₂O₂ in NaOH. The same observation is also recorded with the pyridine complex.

As regards the increase in the titration value in the case of water and closed bottle decomposition, it has been shown by the author and his co-workers^{6,7} that the products

6. *This Journal*, 1957, 24, 59.7. *Rajput and Rai, Ibid.*, 1965, 42, 377.

formed contain Cr (III) besides Cr (VI). These were represented as $\text{Cr}_2(\text{Cr}_2\text{O}_7)_3$ and CrCrO_4 , respectively. On the basis of Schwarz's formula (CrO_3), the decomposition should occur as:

and

with acid.

The total number of oxygen atoms available is thus 28 and in the second case, only 9; their ratio will come up to 28:9, i.e. 3.1:1, whereas the experimental value does not exceed 2.10:1. On the contrary, according to the formula for the blue compound, as suggested by the present author, the decomposition would occur as:

or

i.e., the ratio between the total oxygen atoms and oxygen atoms available from the dichromate stage will be 18:9 or 2:1 or 20:9 or 2.22:1, which is the same as obtained in Table I.

As noted by several workers, alkali chromates are formed if the blue perchromate is decomposed in alkali hydroxides. Now, had it been CrO_3 , it would have decomposed as follows in alkali hydroxide solutions:

and

i.e., the ratio of the available oxygen will be 7:3 or 2.33:1, but the ratios obtained in Table I in the case of NaOH and KOH lie between 1.63 and 1.74. On the other hand, according to the formula suggested by the present author, the decomposition would occur as:

and

or

and the ratio in this case will be 18:12 or 1.5:1, which is close to 1.63, as experimentally observed. Further, the other labile form of the formula, suggested by the author, shows:

or

and the ratio will be 5.3 or 1.66:1 which is very near to the experimental value, shown above.

The large increase in the oxidation value in the case of ammonium hydroxide on oxidation with H_2O_2 in NaOH can be explained on the basis of the formation of complex compounds by transitional elements with power to absorb oxygen⁸.

It is clear that the various ratios obtained in Table I in the case of NaOH/KOH are same as in Table II in the case of pyridine complex when decomposed in water, NaOH or KOH. This shows that the ethereal blue perchromate and its pyridine complex behave similarly. It may therefore be concluded that the blue perchromate contains Cr(III) which supports the formula suggested by the author.

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8. Ballar, "Chemistry of Co-ordination Compounds", J. E. Reinhold Publication, New York, pp.45-46.